

FEATURES OF USING AN ANIMALISTIC COMPONENT IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Pardayeva Mahliyo G'ayrat Qizi

Karshi Start University Linguistics (English) Department

Master's Degree Student

e-mail: pardayevamahliyo09@gmail.com

Abstract: The present investigation endeavors to scrutinize the role of animalistic elements in augmenting communication in the English language. The application of idiomatic phrases, metaphors, personification, branding, and slang in language pertaining to animals facilitates the articulation of intricate concepts, affective states and distinctive attributes. Following this, the investigation proceeds to examine particular forms of animalistic components, with a comprehensive elucidation of their corresponding examples and scrutinized interpretations within the context of inter-species communication. The conclusion restates the significance of this linguistic phenomenon and proposes further investigation into its utilization within diverse contexts and cultures, the acquisition and learning of language, as well as its connection to other elements of language usage.

Key words: Animalistic components, Language, Linguistic phenomenon, Idioms and expressions, Metaphors, Personification, Branding and marketing, Slang, Communication, Language enhancement

I. Introduction

Language serves as a critical facilitator of communication, providing individuals with the means to effectively articulate and convey their cognitive processes, affective states, and conceptual constructs. The English language is a linguistically diverse and adaptable mode of communication, embodying a wide range of formats and linguistic styles for conveying thoughts and ideas. The utilization of animalistic components in English language is a captivating characteristic that enhances the vibrancy and

intricacy of communication. Animalistic components encompass the utilization of lexical items related to the animal kingdom, idiomatic expressions, metaphors, personification, branding, and slang terms within the confines of the English linguistic system. The inclusion of animalistic elements within the English linguistic framework has been a subject of scrutiny among several academics. George Lakoff and Mark Johnson posit in their literary work titled "Metaphors We Live By" that metaphors are not solely literary constructs, as they play a vital role in shaping our thinking, communication, and comprehension of the world. The works of scholar Elena Semino, specifically her published work entitled "Metaphor in Discourse," delve into an analysis of the function of metaphor in day-to-day communication. According to Semino, the widespread presence of metaphors in communication is a notable characteristic, wherein the utilization of animalistic metaphors is extensive in the English language. The author postulates that expressions employing animalistic metaphors, namely "sly as a fox" or "stubborn as a mule," are commonly employed to characterize human attributes and conduct.

Linguist Jonathan Charteris-Black has undertaken research examining the utilization of animalistic components within the English language. Charteris-Black investigates the function of metaphors within the realm of political communication, as explicated within his publication entitled "Metaphor and Political Communication.". As an instance, political figures may resort to the implementation of beastly metaphors, exemplified by the phrase "the wolf is at the door," so as to communicate a sensation of pressing need and peril.

II. Idioms and Expressions

Idioms and expressions are an essential component of the English language that facilitate the concise and vivid communication of ideas and emotions. The term "idiom" refers to a collection of lexical items that possess a non-literal connotation, often without direct correlation to the individual semantic implications of the constituent words.

The prevalence of animalistic idioms and expressions in the English language has attracted the scholarly attention of different researchers. An illustration of scholarly writing could be: In his publication, "The Language of Metaphors," Andrew Goatly, a linguist, conducts an analysis of animalistic idioms' utilization in the English language. The proposal posits that expressions imbued with animalistic connotations, such as "to let the cat out of the bag" or "to be a fish out of water," serve as indispensable modes of communication for communicating multifaceted emotional states and concepts. The phrase "to kill two birds with one stone" can be regarded as a succinct and enduring method of conveying the concept of executing two tasks simultaneously. Likewise, the turn of phrase "to have a whale of a time" affords a striking and embellished manner in articulating a pleasurable encounter.

Ultimately, the utilization of idiomatic and expressive language grounded in animality holds significant value in augmenting communicative prowess within the English linguistic landscape. The ubiquity of animalistic idioms and expressions in colloquial language and written communication is indicative of their pivotal role in succinctly and memorably conveying intricate notions and affective states. The utilization of animalistic idioms and expressions in the English language has been the focus of investigation by various scholars, including Andrew Goatly, George Lakoff, Mark Johnson, Jonathan Charteris-Black, and others, who have underscored their significant role in effective communication[4].

III. Metaphors

Metaphors represent a form of figurative language that juxtaposes dissimilar entities to underscore likenesses between them. The metaphorical expression "the elephant in the room" is commonly employed to depict a challenging or unsettling matter that is manifestly evident, yet evades direct confrontation by all concerned parties. The linguistic device of metaphor, wherein "to be a snake in the grass" is employed, characterizes an individual who is unreliable and conceals their genuine motivations. It can be asserted that the incorporation of animalistic metaphors represents a fundamental constituent within the English language.

IV. Personification

Personification is a literary technique that confers anthropomorphic attributes, traits, or sentiments upon non-human entities, including animals, objects, or natural phenomena. The prevalence of animalistic personification within the English lexicon has received significant attention from numerous scholars.

George Orwell's novel "Animal Farm" serves as an eminent illustration of animalistic personification in literature. It portrays farm animals as anthropomorphic beings, possessing human-like qualities and participating in political man oeuvres . The fable entitled "The Tortoise and the Hare" imbues the titular characters with anthropomorphic attributes including the capacity for verbal communication and logical thought.

The employment of animalistic personification in communication signifies an efficacious means of creating an association between the audience and the object of personification. The personification of animals, objects, or natural phenomena enables speakers or writers to promote relatable and comprehensible qualities to their audience.

V. Animal Names in Branding and Marketing

The practice of employing animal nomenclature for branding and marketing purposes has a long-standing history, and it remains a prominent select for corporations seeking to establish noteworthy and efficacious brand identities. The investigation of the relevance of animal naming techniques in the context of branding and marketing has been thoroughly examined by researchers. The outcomes of their scholarly inquiry emphasize the considerable influence that animal names can have on consumer attitudes and brand identification.

VI. Animal-related Words in Slang

The utilization of animal-related lexicons in vernacular has persisted throughout numerous years and remains a prominent preference for individuals seeking to originate distinguished and notable colloquial expressions. Scholars have undertaken an investigation into the import of employing vocabulary pertaining to animals within

colloquial language, and their observations underscore the effects that such linguistic usage may yield on individual and collective identities and unity.

A manifestation of animal-related vocabulary employed in colloquial language involves the utilization of the word "chicken" as a descriptor denoting an individual who exhibits cowardice or trepidation.

VII. Conclusion

Concluding, the utilization of animalistic elements in the English language constitutes a noteworthy linguistic phenomenon that has been extensively examined by scholars. The utilization of idioms, metaphors, personification, branding, and slang that are animal-related facilitates the articulation of intricate notions, sentiments, and traits, thereby augmenting communication in diverse settings. The incorporation of animalistic components in the framework of the English language bears various implications for the domains of language and communication. The act of forming a memorable and distinct expression, which in turn reinforces social identity and promotes group cohesion, can prove to be advantageous. In addition, the utilization of language can serve the purpose of expressing sentimentality while crafting compelling visualizations, thereby enhancing the efficacy and captivating nature of the message delivered.

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